

Impact of Waterfronts on University Campuses in Eastern Nigeria: A Preliminary Study of UAES' Proposed Waterfront Development

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Received: August 31, 2024; Accepted: September 18, 2024; Published: September 20, 2024

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13820896>

Abstract: The study sets out to investigate the direct impact of establishing a mixed-use water resource facility on the Otammiri river bank of the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences situated at the former estate of the Imo State Polytechnic Umuagwo, Imo State. Data was drawn from the professional firms of Architects, Estate Surveyors and Town planners as well as users of waterfront tourist sites within the state. Retrieved data was analysed using frequency tables and the Relative Importance Index (RII) while findings were discussed. From the perspective of the professionals, of the 17 significant variables, the five most crucial impacts on university campuses were envisaged to be: a boost of tourism and cultural attraction, ecological sustainability, improved internally generated revenue, appreciation in environmental sustainability / outlook and improved quality of life (physical and mental health etc.). On the other hand, the five most crucial impacts envisaged by tourists comprised; access to quality public spaces, provision / preservation of cultural amenities, improved academic research output, improved quality of life (physical and mental health etc.) and boost of tourism and cultural attraction. The study recommends that the University management, the Imo state Government- being owners of the institution and other stakeholders engage and execute the professional counsel of the relevant professionals in ensuring maximized outcomes. Finally, the facility should be made to address the needs of the end users so as to spur sustained patronage and maximized anticipated benefits.

Keywords: *Waterfronts, Otammiri river, UAES, Waterfront Resource Center, Tourist*

Introduction

Waterfronts exist naturally in various forms such as river banks, ocean shore lines, harbors, lake shores, canal sides, harbors, etc (Iwata and Del Rio, 2004). In ancient times, these “portals of globalization” formed on these waterfronts because of the undeniable essence of water to human life (Middell and Naumann, 2010). Besides this, its usefulness in terms of transportation, irrigation, provision of essential minerals and food attracted agriculture (e.g. the Nile basin) trade, commerce which is still visible till date (Middell and Naumann, 2010). Gradually, water side settlements experienced dynamic change in structure and most importantly, functionality due to varied environmental, social and economic factors (Iwata and Del Rio, 2004). In contemporary times, the overhaul of water fronts for varied human use has been made possible by the activities of migrants and stakeholders across several fields (Van-de-Laar, 2020). Professionals within and outside the built environment -politicians, entrepreneurs and other key decision-makers in society have ensured that waterfronts become the exclusive preserve of either the government, the affluent or nouveau-riches in society globally. This is evident in the creation of artificial islands on the Arabian

Gulf, extended water front lines in Lagos (Eko Atlantic), establishment of the Panama and Suez Canals etc. all in a bid to satisfy the unending crave for property development along shore lines (Osterhammel and Patrick, 2014).

Also, in a bid to create humongous profit margins, wealthy investors and developers go to extremes in incorporating waterfronts (artificial or natural) into land-locked communities, earmarked for development, creating a premium in value due to the enhanced functionality and scenery, water bodies impose on adjacent properties. In addition, waterfront developments such as Whispering Palms Resort in Badagry and the waterfront of the University of Lagos act as fantastic locations to unwind and relax, as well as provide excellent public spaces in the form of prime hospitality and residential estates for residents to leisurely explore their natural environment.

Furthermore, the renewed attention and growing interest on environmental issues, coupled with the increased desire for the development of water-based leisure activities in public parks and more so, the need to drive Internally Generated Revenue (IGR) across Nigeria, many stakeholders now influence decisions to build waterfronts. The Otammiri River front is one of such numerous waterfront real estates

in Imo state, lying fallow, wasting away but earnestly yearning for development from its varied current use ranging from a waste site, sand mine and waterhole for nomadic cattle herders.

In recent times, the maximization of waterfronts is being intensified in bringing formerly obscure fishing settlements and cities to international relevance via tourism (Ali *et al.*, 2020). Thus, the need to develop comprehensive strategies in developing viable waterfronts for future development is crucial. In line with Ali, Mohamed and El. Sohafi (2020), the need for concerned stakeholders in the built and unbuilt environments to propose and develop feasible frameworks for the transformation and development of sections of the Otammiri waterfront for local, national and international relevance is now. On this premise lies the weight of this study.

Extant literature on water resource development is interdisciplinary and increasingly becoming a topical issue of conversation within the fields of urban planning, architecture, real estate and geography (Üzümçüođlu and Mukaddes 2022).

The aspects researched over the year include but not limited to: the nature of waterfronts (Timur, 2013), categories of waterfront developments (Eves *et al.*, 2011), impact of

waterfronts on settlements in proximity (Üzümçüođlu and Mukaddes 2022), redesigning waterfront developments (Gospodini, 2001; Davidson, N.D), waterfront redevelopment in urban public spaces (Al-Shams *et al.*, 2013) and sustainable waterfront principles and development (Ali *et al.*, 2020; Istiaque *et al.*, 2018; Peter and Ulrich, 2000; Giovinazzi and Giovinazzi 2008).

These aspects of research have proven that waterfronts are competitive for land uses which may make them difficult to manage (Gospodini, 2001). Competing land use in conflict invariably create a plethora of challenges which include pollution of varied categories and types, severe abuse as a free gift of nature, water logging and encroachment. Reordering complementary land use through technology, multi-zoning enables the achievement of scenery and sustainable waterfronts (Istiaque *et al.*, 2018; Üzümçüođlu and Mukaddes, 2022). Mixed land developments such as recreational, commercial and residential land use sandwiched between heritage and new buildings promote economic and aesthetic value while fostering a reflection of culture, identity of waterfront societies (Al-Shams *et al.*, 2013).

There is a dearth of Nigerian literature on the subject of sustainable waterfront

developments and as such, this current study seeks to complement existing studies and also, investigate the impact of these waterfront developments on host communities.

Materials and Methods

Area of Study

The Otammiri River is estimated to be 30km long and a major river in Imo state. From its origin in Egbu, it transverses many communities in the state including Nekede, Ihiagwa and Umuagwo, flowing into the Atlantic Ocean through Ozuzu in Etchee Local Government Area of Rivers state. It

has a water-shed of about 10,000 km², which is mostly covered by depleted rain forest vegetation and has a mean temperature of around 27°C throughout the year. The river is subject to intense human and industrial activities and yet, provides drinking water for some communities. Observation revealed that waste generated from Avu, located at the outer metropolitan Owerri, is dumped along the river bank in Owerri West LGA along Port-Harcourt highway. The dumpsite which is adjacent to the river pollutes much of the water after which, it flows down to Umuagwo (Temitope, 2016).

Fig. 1 Site for the Proposed UAES Waterfront Resource Center Source: Authors' Reconnaissance Survey

The Proposed UAES Otammiri River Waterfront Resource Center Project

A reconnaissance drone survey of the entire river course delineating the rear of the UAES campus, showed a suitable site for the UAES-WRC accessible from the

Campus Catholic church. This proposed site afforded the greatest expanse of undeveloped waterfront, adequate water volume with minimum cost for dredging as well as depth for sporting and recreational activities. The proposed 7.5

hectare expanse of farm land providing ample opportunities for accommodating other ancillary developments as envisaged,

planned and shown in Figures 2 and 3 below.

Fig. 2 Land Use allocation for the Proposed UAES Waterfront Resource Center (WRC) Source: Authors' Construct (2023).

As envisaged in the proposed development, Figure 2 identifies and illustrates the land use allocation within the proposed waterfront facility. These includes a green areas for lawns, golf courses and gardens. Residential / commercial charlets – 20 units of 3 bedroom bungalows, a club house,

resource center with provision for 2 rentable halls, a marina to access water sporting, outdoor games and a charming river bank for leisure and relaxation. A host of other suitable commercial activities are being envisaged to ensure that the facility is sustainable and self sufficient.

Fig. 3 Proposed UAES Waterfront Resource Center (WRC) Source: Authors' Construct (2023).

The abutting Otammiri river waterfront which has been abused, being the case study of this research, is no different from any other in India and elsewhere which have been abused but finally rehabilitated and developed for sustained economic and aesthetic values.

Methods

Data for the study was retrieved from respondents which comprised – principal professionals within the built environment as well as tourists in South Eastern Nigeria using a structured online survey administered using social media. Specific professional online platforms were targeted using whatsapp to effectively reach the desired population. The professional respondents comprised: Principal partners/representatives of Architectural

firms, Estate Surveying and Valuation firms as well as those of Urban and Regional Planning firms.

Of the gamut of professionals in the built environment, the architects, planners and estate surveyors were chosen for this study due to their specialized functions. Architectural firms are responsible for the architectural concept, design, drafting and the production of the final drawings for which builders use in executing the production of such developments on site. On the other hand, Town planning firms/planners are known to order land use within communities ensuring that land use is situated in locations which would afford not only its best and highest use but also, complement existing neighbouring land uses. Finally, estate surveying firms specialize in offering services in the aspect

of property, facilities and space management to ensure real estate investments yield maximum returns sustainably to the investor via effective managerial skills. Therefore, their stake in the design, establishment and management of waterfront developments cannot be overlooked.

Population for the study comprised all professionally registered practicing architectural, estate surveying and valuation inclusive of Urban and Regional Planning firms nationwide. These amounted to 1176, 1146, 457 firms respectively (NIA Directory, N.D; NIESV online Directory, 2024; TOPREC online Directory, 2024).

For the sampling frame, all professionally registered practicing architectural, estate

surveying and urban planning firms within the 5 states geographically referred to as the South East of Nigeria - Anambra, Abia, Ebonyin, Enugu and Imo were adopted Umeh (2018). Thus, 72 architectural firms, 85 estate surveying firms and 58 Urban Planning firms were identified. Due to the manageability of the Sampling frame, the same number were each adopted as Sample size for the various professional firms.

Thereafter, the results were tabularised and the mean of individual variable ranked to ascertain the most impactful benefit of the university waterfront. Table 1 presents the summary of the various population considered for the study as well as the various response rate retrieved.

Table 1 Response rate of Principal Professionals within the Built Environment.

Respondents	Population	Population Size (States)		Sample Frame	Sample Size	Response	Response Rate (%)
Professionals in the Built Environment involved in the study	Architects (1,176)	Anambra		72	72	37	51.4
		Abia					
		Ebonyin					
		Enugu					
		Imo					
	Estate Surveying Firms (1,146)	Anambra	17	85	85	49	57.6
		Abia	15				
		Ebonyin	0				
		Enugu	41				
		Imo	12				
	Urban & Regional Planning Firms (457)	Anambra	16	58	58	31	53.4
		Abia	15				
		Ebonyi	2				
		Enugu	22				
		Imo	13				

Authors' Fieldwork Analysis, 2024

In the same vein, the same survey tool was disseminated online amongst tourist /

tourism enthusiasts conversant with waterfront developments in Imo State and

beyond. In generating the study population for this set of respondents, the average number of tourists visiting a similar site in the state (Oguta Lake Resorts) on a weekend / weekly basis was investigated during prior pilot visits to the facility. It was discovered that the prevalence of vices such as those of oil bunkery, illegal oil refining activities within the creeks and other security concerns as evidenced by a heightened military presence in the locality had since caused a drastic drop in tourists from an average of 1050 - 1250 (few years ago) to

scarcely between 150 and 300 during weekends. The drastic drop in tourists was further observed to probably have partly caused the abandonment of the Oguta Lake golf course / resort project initiated by the State Government about 8 years ago. Thus, for this study, the study population constitutes 1,250 tourists while the sampling frame considered is 300. This figure is further adopted as the sample size due to its manageability. These facts are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2 Response rate of Tourism Enthusiasts.

Respondents	Population	Sampling Frame	Sample Size	Response	Response Rate (%)
Tourists	1,250	300	300	269	89.66%

Authors' Fieldwork Analysis, 2024

Data Presentation

In accomplishing the aim of this study, the descriptive data retrieved was presented in terms of demographical characteristics of the respondents using frequency tables and mean while the Relative Importance Index (RII) was used in measuring and ranking each variable. In determining the RII, the researcher determined the weighted arithmetic mean by assigning various digits to specific terms as described below:

- 1 – Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Disagree
- 3 - Neutral
- 4 - Agree

5 – Strongly Agree

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents – Sex Distribution

Based on the survey analysis, it was discovered that males exceeded females amongst all categories of the respondents. Amongst the 37 Architects, 23 (representing 62 percent) were found to be males while the rest 14 (38%) were identified as females. Of the total of 49 Estate Surveyors, 37 (representing 76 percent) were males while females were 12 (representing 24 percent) of the respondents. In the same vein, of the 31

planners, there were 19 (representing 61 percent) male while 12 persons - constituting 39 percent were found to be females. The dominance of the male sex in all three professional disciplines maybe as a result of the tedious nature of the disciplines both at the training and professional levels

as females may opt for the less demanding disciplines based on their peculiar nature and the demands of motherhood. Table 3 below presents the summary for the gender distribution within the four different categories of respondents.

Table 3 Gender Distribution amongst all categories of Respondents

	Respondents Type / Response Rate				
	Firms			Tourists	Total
Sex	Architects	Estate surveyors	Planners		
Male	23 (62%)	37 (76%)	19 (61%)	168 (62%)	247 (64%)
Female	14 (38%)	12 (24%)	12 (39%)	101 (38%)	139 (36%)
Total	37 (100%)	49 (100%)	31 (100%)	269 (100%)	386 (100%)

Authors' Fieldwork Analysis, 2024

Furthermore, the tourist category of respondents comprised a total of 269 persons. This set of individuals were found to be dominated by males. Of this number, 168 representing 62% were found to be male folks while the remainder 38% (101 persons) were females. In total, of the 386 respondents sampled, 64 percent (247 persons) were identified as males while 36 percent (139 persons) were females. This maybe indicative of the fact that the demands of motherhood as well as the occupational mobility of the male folk in catering for the home-front may have been the reason why fewer females were on the

go unlike the male folks who were much freer and available for adventure.

Age of Respondents – Professionals and Tourists

In analysing the ages of respondents within ranges, five different age brackets capturing the ages between 21years and 61 years + were established. A close observation shows that majority of the respondents fell into the age bracket of between 41 to 50 years of age with an exception to estate surveyors where the age bracket of 31 to 40 years dominated the sampled majority. This majority accounted for 48% (187 persons) of the entire valid 386 respondents.

Table 4 Age of Respondents – Professionals and Tourists

Age (Years)	Respondents Type / Response Rate				
	Architects Freq. (%)	Estate Surveyors Freq. (%)	Planners Freq. (%)	Tourists Freq. (%)	Total (%)

21 – 30	2 (5%)	6 (12%)	-	5 (2%)	19 (5%)
31 – 40	8 (22%)	15 (31%)	6 (19%)	46 (17%)	75 (19%)
41 – 50	21 (57%)	14 (29%)	23 (75%)	129 (48%)	187 (48%)
51 – 60	6 (16%)	12 (24%)	1 (3%)	82 (30%)	95 (25%)
61 +	-	2 (4%)	1 (3%)	7 (3%)	10 (3%)
Total	37 (100%)	49 (100%)	31 (100%)	269 (100%)	386 (100%)

Authors’ Fieldwork Analysis, 2024

Amongst the architects, 57percent (21 persons) of the respondents were within the age bracket of 41-50 years. This was followed by the age bracket of 31-40 years which comprised 22 percent (8 persons) while the age bracket of 51-60 years followed comprising of 16 percent (6 persons) of the 37 architects sampled. Finally, within the architects, only 2 persons (5 percent) within the age group of 21-30years volunteered to partake of the study. This infers that 95 percent (asides the age bracket of 21-30years) of the respondents were experienced and versatile professionals capable of proffering practical solutions to issues relating to the study.

Unlike the pattern of responses for architects, the age bracket for the most responsive estate surveyors was that of 31-40 years (15 persons) representing 31percent of the respondents. Though, this set was found slightly higher than the responses retrieved from the age bracket of 41-50 years (14 persons) signifying 29percent, there are indications that these individuals/firms are “most vibrant and tenaciously” aiming at having a good share

of the real estate market. Next in line, were the age brackets of 51-60 years - found to responsive by 24percent (12 persons), 21-30 years (6 persons representing 12percent of estate surveyors) and finally, the age bracket of 61+ years (2 persons representing 4percent). Inferences show that, 88 percent of responses were received from estate surveyors within the “vibrant and accomplished” cadre of professionalism. Thus, their position on issues relating to the study can largely be relied upon.

For principals / representatives of Town planning firms, of the 31 respondents, 23 respondents, (representing 75percent) where found to belong to the age bracket of 41-50 years of age while the age bracket of 31-40 years (6 persons representing 19percent of the population) constituted the second most significant age group. For the age brackets of 41-50 years and 61 years+, there was a tie for the position of least response as each comprised 1 person (representing 3percent of the population). Based on observations, all respondents (town planers) for this study could be termed to fall within the “vibrant” and “accomplished” cadre of

professionalism. Therefore, their stand on issues relating to urban and country planning can help in shaping the current study.

For the 269 tourists who constitute users of Water front resorts and leisure centers, 129 tourists (forming the majority of 48percent) were found to belong to the age bracket of 41- 50 years of age. This was followed by the age bracket of 51-60 years (82 persons representing 30percent) while the age brackets of 31-40 years and 61 years + constituted 46 persons (representing 17percent) and 7 persons (representing 3percent) of the population of planners respectively. The least significant response was retrieved from the age bracket of 21-30 years. This minuscule group comprised 2percent (representing 5 persons) of the 269

town planners sampled. Based on deductions, active working class individuals (31-60 years) were the highest users/patronizers of waterfront centers. This was then followed by Senior citizens who were close to retirement or retired as depicted by the age range of 61 years and above. More emphasis on the manner of occupation, these tourists engage in would further be analysed in 5.3.

Occupational Characteristics of the Tourist.

In a bid to understand the demographics of tourists, there was the need to request of the occupational status of the users of waterfront leisure centers. At a glance, Table 5 presents, the multi-facet nature of occupation, for this set of respondents.

Table 5 Occupational Status of the Tourists

Respondents	Occupation Characteristic	Frequency	Sample Size	Total Response	Response Rate (%)
Tourists	Pilot	3 (1%)	300	269	89.66
	Clergy	5 (2%)			
	Engineers / Project Mgt.	11 (4%)			
	Journalist	9 (3%)			
	Civil / Public Servants	7 (2.6%)			
	I.T. specialist	33 (12.3%)4			
	Medical Professionals	21 (7.8%)6			
	Tourism Consultants	7 (2.6%)			
	Business / Accountants	40 (14.9%)2			
	Petroleum Industry	46 (17%)1			
	Entrepreneur	39 (14.5%)3			
	Logistics	20 (7.4%)7			
Education	28 (10.4%)5				

Authors’ Fieldwork Analysis, 2024

Table 5 indicates that the highest patronizers of waterfront leisure centers within Imo state

were professionals within the Petroleum industry. This was most significant by

17percent (46 persons). This was followed by professionals within the spheres of Business and Accountancy with a significance of 14.9percent (40 persons). Waterfront tourists who were private businessmen (entrepreneurs) ranked the third largest group with a significance of 14.5percent (39 persons). This was closely followed by specialists in the I.T. industry forming the fourth most significant group by 12.3percent (33 persons representing 12.4percent). In order of significance, other major professionals include Educationists (10.4percent representing 28 persons), Medical professionals (7.8percent representing 21 persons) and logistics (7.4percent representing 20 persons).

Respondents within the minor occupations as represented in the Table include the eight most significant – Engineers/Project managers (4percent representing 11 persons) while the ninth significant occupation was Journalism (3percent representing 9 persons). At the tenth most represented occupation, there was a tie between the duo of public/civil servants and tourism consultants. Both professions were each represented by 2.6percent representing 7 of the 269 tourists). Clergymen were eleventh

most significant occupation as represented by 2percent (5 persons while the least most represented occupation were pilots with a 1percent representation (3 persons).

This sequence of the aforementioned result was expected as a prior pilot study had revealed that until of late, water front resorts around the Oguta Lake axis were most patronized by petroleum industry staff (the first most significant occupation) which also included accountants and business managers (the second most significant occupation) from the neighboring Port Harcourt for golfing and relaxation during the weekend. These had meeting and dealing with private businessmen (the third most significant occupation) and I.T. specialists (the fourth most significant occupation). The other professional were most likely present for other reasons other than business thus were of scanty representation.

Highest Education Qualification of Respondents

Finally, the highest academic qualification of all four respondent groups was also required and same was supplied. Table 6 presents the varied qualifications of all four groups at a glance.

Table 6: Highest Education Qualification of all four groups of Respondents

Age	Respondents Type / Response Rate				Total
	Architects	Estate Surveyors	Planners	Tourists	

FSLC	-	-	-	-	-
ND	-	-	-	-	-
HND/BSc	9 (24%)	31 (63%)	27 (87%)	47 (17%)	114 (30%)
MSc/MBA	15 (41%)	11 (23%)	4 (13%)	193 (72%)	223 (58%)
PhD	13 (35%)	7 (14%)	-	29 (11%)	49 (12%)
Total	37 (100%)	49 (100%)	31 (100%)	269 (100%)	386 (100%)

Authors' Fieldwork Analysis, 2024

Of the 37 architects, majority had a second degree holders. This was indicated by a 41percent (representing 15 persons) representation. This position was followed by Doctorate degree holders having a 35percent (13 persons) representation. Finally, Higher National Degree holders/ first degree holders were ranked third place as represented by a 24percent (9 persons) representation. As a pre-requisite to professional registration, first degree holders of Architecture are required to have a second degree. This seems to be the reason for the surge in number for second degree holders of Architecture in Table 6.

Amongst the respondent group of 49 Estate Surveying firms composed of principal partners or their representatives, majority of them only had first degrees or Higher National Diplomas. This was represented by a 65percent (31 persons) share. A second degree was held by a mere 23percent (11 persons) while only a pantry number of 7 persons (constituting 14percent) held a doctorate. The above analysis show that the profession of Estate management is made up of mostly practitioners as indicated by

mostly HND/first and second degree holders as against academicians having doctorate degrees.

The profession of town planning is peculiarly different in trend. Of the 31 respondents, the vast majority of principal partners or their representatives (87percent representing 27 persons) had either a Higher National Diploma (HND) or its equivalent degree (BSc). The rest 13percent (4 persons) had a Masters degree. This largely indicates that the majority of town planners seem to practice the profession fully while a handful opt for a second degree for the sake of personal advancement or in pursuit of a future in the academia.

The last respondent group consisting of 269 tourists largely comprised second degree holders (MSc and MBA). This segment constituted 72percent of tourists while the second most popular qualification was the Higher National Diploma and its equivalent degree (HND/BSc) with a quota share of 17percent (47 persons). Finally, 11percent (29 persons) were doctorate degree holders in their respective field of endeavors. This analysis may indicate that majority of the

respondents' occupied managerial positions in industry while others were into a form of professional practice of sorts. Only the few were concerned with academics as signified by their doctorate degrees. No tourist was found with the lower cadre of academic qualifications such as the First Leaving School Certificate and the Ordinary National Diploma. This was the same for the other group of respondents.

Impact of Sustainable University Waterfront Development on its Host Community

The potential impact of University waterfront developments on the immediate host community was measured from two perspectives. First, the perspective of the group of professionals involved in the survey was ascertained as well as those of the tourists.

The presentation and analysis of the responses as given by the professionals are tabulated in Table 7.

Table 7 Perspective of Professionals – Architects, Estate Surveyors and Town Planners

S/N	Variables	Frequency					Total	Mean Score	Rank
		SD	D	N	A	SA			
		1	2	3	4	5			
1.	Boost of tourism potential /cultural attraction	--	--	2[6]	33[132]	82[410]	117[548]	4.6838	1 st
2.	Improved access to the University	2[2]	7[14]	16[48]	47[188]	45[225]	117[477]	4.0769	14 th
3.	Improved University publicity / acceptability	--	3[6]	13[39]	42[168]	59[295]	117[508]	4.3419	8 th
4.	Improved academic research output/product	--	--	8[24]	54[216]	55[275]	117[515]	4.4017	*6 th
5.	Protection of university coast line	--	2[4]	23[69]	37[148]	55[275]	117[496]	4.2393	9 th
6.	Appreciation in Environmental sustainability / outlook	2[2]	2[4]	3[9]	41[164]	69[345]	117[524]	4.4786	4 th
7.	Improved Internally Generated Revenue	--	2[4]	5[15]	46[188]	64[320]	117[527]	4.5043	3 rd
8.	Improved state tax	--	8[16]	20[60]	36[144]	53[265]	117[485]	4.1453	13 th
9.	Ecological sustainability	--	0[0]	8[24]	36[144]	73[365]	117[533]	4.5556	2 nd
10.	Social equity	--	3[6]	26[78]	52[208]	36[180]	117[472]	4.0342	15 th
11.	Improved cohesion and Inclusivity	--	3(6)	28(84)	54[216]	32[160]	117[466]	3.9829	16 th
12.	Integrated planning and management	--	2(4)	19(57)	52[208]	44[220]	117[489]	4.1795	11 th
13.	Provision and preservation of Cultural amenities	--	3(6)	11(33)	68[272]	35[175]	117[486]	4.1538	12 th
14.	Improved quality of life (physical and mental health etc.)	--	3(6)	3(9)	54[216]	57[285]	117[516]	4.4103	5 th
15.	Access to quality public spaces	--	2(4)	3(9)	58[232]	54[270]	117[515]	4.4017	*6 th

16.	Zoning / Land use planning	--	3(6)	15(45)	55[220]	44[220]	117[491]	4.1966	10 th
17.	Improvement of land adjacent value	2(2)	--	7(21)	54[216]	54[270]	117[509]	4.3504	7 th

Where SD = Strongly Disagree, D = Disagree, N = Neutral, A = Agree and SA = Strongly Agree

Authors' Fieldwork Analysis, 2024.

Analysis from Table 7 indicates that professionals are strongly of the opinion that university water front developments boost the tourism potential /cultural attraction of the host community. This was ranked first with a mean score of 4.6838.

The second most popular variable was ecological sustainability with a mean score of 4.5556 while improved internally generated revenue for the host university community was rated in third place with a mean score of 4.5043. The fourth most popular variable linked to university water front developments was appreciation in environmental sustainability / outlook with a mean score of 4.4786 while improved quality of life for the university community (physical and mental health etc.) was rated the fifth most attested variable with a mean score of 4.4103.

For the sixth most popular variable, the duo of improved academic research output and access to quality public spaces tied the position with a mean score of 4.4017 while improvement of adjacent land value was rated seventh position with a mean score of 4.3504. In addition, the variables of improved university publicity / acceptability

and protection of university coast line were each rated in the eighth and ninth place each with mean scores of 4.3419 and 4.2393 respectively.

In the same vein, university campuses with waterfront developments were found to possess evidence of zoning / land use planning as well as integrated planning and management. These variables were individually ranked in the tenth and eleventh position with mean scores of 4.1966 and 4.1795 respectively. Furthermore, for the rank of twelfth and thirteenth positions, provision and preservation of cultural amenities (with a mean score of 4.1538) and improved state tax (with a mean score of 4.1453) were opined to be popular.

Yet again, respondents within the group of professionals opined that improved access to the university and social equity each ranked fourteenth and fifteenth position with each having a means score of 4.0769 and 4.0342 respectively. Finally, the least popular variable of improved cohesion and inclusivity with a mean score of 3.9829 was ranked sixteenth overall. Thus, all variables were deemed important but with slight discrepancy in the mean score of each.

Table 8 The Perspective of Tourists / Tourism Enthusiasts

S/N	Options	SD	D	N	A	SA	Total	Mean	Rank
		1	2	3	4	5			
1.	Boost of tourism potential /cultural attraction	-	-	42[126]	90[360]	137[685]	269[1,171]	4.3532	5 th
2.	Improved access to the University	-	19[38]	37[111]	105[420]	108[540]	269[1,109]	4.1227	15 th
3.	Improved University publicity / acceptability	-	7[14]	30[90]	135[540]	97[485]	269[1,129]	4.1970	12 th
4.	Improved academic research output	-	-	19[57]	127[508]	123[615]	269[1,180]	4.3866	3 rd
5.	Protection of university coast line	-	4[8]	52[156]	127[508]	86[430]	269[1,102]	4.0967	16 th
6.	Appreciation in Environmental sustainability / outlook	-	8[16]	7[21]	161[644]	93[465]	269[1,146]	4.2602	10 th
7.	Improved Internally Generated Revenue	-	4[8]	11[33]	149[596]	105[525]	269[1,162]	4.3197	8 th
8.	Improved state tax.	-	19[38]	45[135]	123[492]	82[410]	269[1,075]	3.9963	17 th
9.	Ecological sustainability	-	-	19[57]	168[672]	82[410]	269[1,139]	4.3242	7 th
10.	Social equity	-	7[14]	60[180]	82[328]	120[600]	269[1,122]	4.1710	13 th
11.	Improved cohesion and Inclusivity	-	7[14]	64[192]	75[300]	123[615]	269[1,121]	4.1673	14 th
12.	Integrated planning and management	-	4[8]	44[132]	101[404]	120[600]	269[1,144]	4.2528	11 th
13.	Provision / preservation of Cultural amenities	-	7[14]	26[78]	78[312]	158[790]	269[1,194]	4.4387	2 nd
14.	Improved quality of life (physical and mental health etc.)	-	7[14]	7[21]	131[524]	124[620]	269[1,179]	4.3829	4 th
15.	Access to quality public spaces	-	4[8]	7[21]	123[492]	135[675]	269[1,196]	4.4461	1 st
16.	Zoning / Land use planning	-	7[14]	34[102]	101[404]	127[635]	269[1,155]	4.2937	9 th
17.	Improvement of land adjacent value	-	4[4]	19[57]	123[492]	123[615]	269[1,168]	4.3420	6 th

Where SD = Strongly Disagree, D = Disagree, N = Neutral, A = Agree and SA = Strongly Agree

Authors' Fieldwork Analysis, 2024

Analysis from the perspective of the tourists as presented in Table 8 signified that the variable of access to quality public spaces was rated the most beneficial impact of waterfronts on university campuses with a mean score of 4.4461. The second most impactful variable was indicated to be the

provision and preservation of cultural amenities with a mean score of 4.4387 while in third place, improved academic research output was graded with a mean score of 4.3866.

The variable of improved quality of life (physical and mental health etc.) for the

immediate university community was judged the fourth most with a mean score of 4.3829 while a boost in tourism potential/cultural attraction was rated fifth most impactful with a mean score of 4.3532.

Furthermore, the variable of improvement of adjacent land value was rated sixth in terms of importance with a mean score of 4.3420 while ecological sustainability was ranked seventh position with a mean score of 4.3242.

Similarly, with a mean score of 4.3197, the variable of improved internally generated revenue was ranked as the eighth most relevant while respondents agreed that *zoning / land use planning* was the ninth most important factor when waterfronts are located in universities. This variable was ranked with a mean score of 4.2937.

Of the seventeen variables, appreciation in environmental sustainability / outlook was ranked the tenth most important variable with a mean score of 4.2602 while the eleventh most significant variable was generally accepted to be integrated planning and management with a mean score of 4.2528.

Again, respondents opined that improved university publicity / acceptability was the ranked the twelfth most popular variable with a mean score of 4.1970 while social

equity having a mean score of 4.1710 ranked thirteenth position. In the same vein, respondent alluded that improved cohesion and inclusivity ranked fourteenth position with a mean score of 4.1673 while the fifteenth most popular variable was improved access to university.

Finally, the second to the least most popular variable was opined to be the variable of protection of university coast line with a mean score of 4.0967 while the least most popular variable was pin pointed to be improved state tax with a mean score of 3.9963.

Findings

Indications from analysis show that from the perspective of professionals, all 17 variables were significant impacts generated by the proposed water front development though at different levels. In order of significance, the impacts posed by the proposed development were envisaged to be: boost in tourism potential /cultural attraction, ecological sustainability, improved internally generated revenue, appreciation in environmental sustainability / outlook as well as improved quality of life (physical and mental health etc.). Afterwards, improved academic research output and access to quality public spaces were of equal importance. Next in line were, improvement of adjacent land

value, improved university publicity / acceptability, protection of university coast line and then, zoning / land use planning. Notably, these findings were in line with those of Chafid (2002) and Bet-El-Silisna (2013). In addition, the next six impacts according to significance levels, were identified to be integrated planning and management, provision and preservation of cultural amenities, improved state tax, improved access to the University, social equity and improved cohesion and inclusivity.

Similar to the responses of the professionals, the tourists agreed that all 17 variables were significant in impact but in a different order. Access to quality public spaces was potentially found to be the most beneficial attribute of a waterfront development. This was followed by provision / preservation of cultural amenities, improved academic research output, improved quality of life (physical and mental health etc.), boost of tourism potential / cultural attraction and improvement of adjacent land value.

As prioritized by the tourists, other benefits in accordance to significance were ecological sustainability, improved internally generated revenue, zoning / land use planning, appreciation in environmental sustainability / outlook, integrated planning and management and improved university

publicity / acceptability. Finally, the least five benefits created by university waterfronts comprised social equity, improved cohesion and inclusivity, improved access to the university, protection of university coast line while improved state tax was considered the least significant benefit.

Conclusion and Recommendations

As a preliminary study, this paper examined the impact of waterfronts on universities in Eastern Nigeria with emphasis on the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, (UAES), Umuagwo situated in Imo state. Professionals concerned with the design, planning, development and management of waterfront developments as well as tourists who frequent waterfronts regularly comprised the study population. The outcome of the research proved that the five most crucial impact on university campuses as perceived by professionals were; boost of tourism and cultural attraction, ecological sustainability, improved internally generated revenue, appreciation in environmental sustainability / outlook and improved quality of life (physical and mental health etc.). On the other hand, the five most crucial impacts recognized by tourists comprised; access to quality public spaces, provision /

preservation of cultural amenities, improved academic research output, improved quality of life (physical and mental health etc.) and boost of tourism and cultural attraction. Based on the responses of both parties, two impacts namely; improved quality of life (physical and mental health etc.) and boost of tourism and cultural attraction appear common between both groups signifying the prominence of both in impacts as created by university waterfronts.

Grounded on these findings, the study recommends that the Management of the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences (UAES) ensures that the counsel of the relevant built environment professionals as well as the expectations of end users of the project are incorporated in all stages of the project to ensure that, the desired outcomes, as discovered by this study, are achieved. Thus, the project must ultimately be people centered. This appeal is also extended to the Imo government and non-governmental stakeholders that would be consulted, in the course of executing the project in order to maximize the benefit the developments has been foreseen to create. Finally, the development must boost tourism, cultural attractions and improve the quality of life for the university residents through viable and intriguing waterfront leisure facilities

and amenities for the development to be deemed to have accomplished its purpose.

Acknowledgement

The authors appreciate Tertiary Education Tax Fund (Tetfund) for the 2022 Institutional Based Research (IBR) Grant received at the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo (UAES), Imo State for the accomplishment of this reconnaissance study as well as the publication of its findings.

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